

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20838785

RUWA ABOKAN AIKI: GURBIN RUWA A KARIN MAGANAR HAUSA

Nana Ibrahim¹; Sadiya Abdullahi Gusau² & Nuruddeen Abubakar³

Department of Hausa

Shehu Shagari College Of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria

¹Email:nanaibrahim6090@gmail.com/ Phone No:234-7034970848

²Phone No: 234-8036246974

³E-mail: babansadik65@gmail.com/ Phone No: 234-8065936327

ABSTRACT

Hausa oral literature is a vast and inexhaustible field of study. As scholars have frequently observed, it serves as a mirror that reflects virtually every aspect of human life and society. This paper, titled “Ruwa Abokan Aiki: Gurbin Ruwa a Karin Maganar Hausa” examines selected Hausa proverbs that relate to water. Water is one of the greatest blessings bestowed by Almighty Allah upon humankind and other living creatures on earth. The study employed library research methods, including the consultation of relevant books, visits to libraries, and interviews with knowledgeable scholars. The objective of the research is to highlight the creativity and wisdom of the Hausa people in formulating proverbs that convey meanings and lessons through references to water. The paper collected and analyzed a number of Hausa proverbs containing water-related expressions and explored their meanings and implications. Findings reveal that Hausa proverbs embody profound wisdom and cultural knowledge, with water serving as an important symbol through which various lessons, values, and experiences are communicated. The study concludes that Hausa proverbs are rich repositories of wisdom and cultural knowledge, as exemplified by the proverb, “Underground water is only found by the one who digs for it,” which underscores the values of determination, hard work, and perseverance, while also illustrating the depth of meaning embedded in Hausa proverbial expressions that can only be fully appreciated through careful analysis and interpretation.

Tsakure

Adabin bakan Hausa wani daji ne mai wuyar kurewa, kuma kamar yadda masana suka sha fada madubi ne wanda yake kallon komi da kowa a wannan rayuwa, wato kusan bai bar komi ba. Wannan takarda mai taken “**Ruwa Abokan Aiki: Gurbin Ruwa a Karin Maganar Hausa**” ta hango wasu bayanai na karin maganar Hausa da suka shafi ruwa. Ruwa na daya daga cikin manyan kyaututtukkan da Allah Madaukakin Sarki Ya bai wa dan Adam da sauran halittun da suke rayuwa a bayan kasa. An yi amfani da litattafai da ziyarar dakunan karatu da tuntuɓar malamai domin hada Wannan takarda. Dalilin wannan bincike shi ne domin a fito da irin fasahar da Allah ya baiwa al’ummar Hausawa na kirƙirar karin maganar da suka yi bayani a kan ruwa. Takardar ta kalato wasu karin maganganun Hausa, waƙanda suka kunshi muhimman bayanai a

kan ruwa. An yi bayani a kan karin maganganu da Hausawa suka ambaci ruwa a cikinsu, kamar yadda bayani ya tabbatar a kasa. Sakamakon binciken ya nuna cewa lalle ruwa na kasa sai ga wanda bai tona ba wato, akwai hikimomi daban daban a cikin karin maganar Hausawa waɗanda na ruwa na daga cikinsu.

1. Gabatarwa

Kowane fanni ko ɓangare na adabin bakan Hausa an karkasa shi domin nazarinsa. Haka ita ma karin maganar Hausa an rarraba ta kashi-kashi dangane da yadda aka gina ta da yanayin manufar da ake son a cimma. Wasu sun karkasa ta, ta la'akari da amfaninta ga al'umma. Misali, akwai masu kyautata halin ɗan Adam da masu karkafa zuciya da masu fadakarwa da ilmantarwa da nishadantarwa da sauransu. Karin magana tana da amfani ga al'ummar Hausawa musamman waɗanda suke amfani da ita tare da bin karantarwata. A cikin al'adu da hikimomin Hausa na gargajiya, karin magana na da manufar bayyana al'adun Hausawa da kuma yadda rayuwarsu take. Al'adun sun haɗa da; na zumunta da gargadi ko nasiha da raha da kuma sana'o'i.

Wannan takarda ta yi nazarin yadda karin maganar Hausa ta taka rawar gani wajen bayyana samuwar 'ruwa' wanda yake da amfani da kuma muhimmanci ga kowane rayuwa ta mutum da dabba da kwari da itace, da tsirrai, da sauran abubuwa. Akwai gabatarwa a matsayin kashi na farko, kashi na biyu kuwa an duba ma'anar karin magana. A kashi na uku an bayyana ma'anar ruwa a mahangar ilimi. Kashi na huɗu takardar ta yi bayanai a kan irin yadda amfani da ruwa ya mamaye wasu karin maganar Hausa da yadda aka yi amfani da shi/su. A kashi na biyar kuwa, jawabin kammalawa ne aka cikasa takardar da shi tare da manazarta.

2. Ma'anar Karin Magana

Da Bahaushe ya ce karin magana, to kalmomi ne guda biyu a haɗe waje ɗaya. A nan 'karin' yana nufin kakkarya magana da Hausawa suke yi domin ta ba da wata ma'ana. Saboda idan an yi bayanin karin magana za a ga zance ne gajere, amma tare da bayani mai yawa. 'Magana' ita ce zance na yau da kullum.

Masana da dama sun bayyana tasu fahimta a kan abin da ake nufi da karin magana. Daga cikin masanan da aka samu bayanin da suka kawo akwai;

Dangambo (1984) ya ce:

“Karin magana dabara ce ta dunkule magana mai yawa a cikin zance ko ‘yan kalmomi kaɗan, cikin hikima”

Zarruƙ da wasu (1986), sun bayyana ma'anar karin magana da cewa:

“Gajeren zance ne wanda yake furshe da hikima”

Danyaya (2007), cewa ya yi:

“Karin magana zance ne gajere, mai fadakarwa kan zancen duniya”

Koko (2011), tana da ra'ayin cewa:

“Karin magana wani salo ne na baje kolin hajar tunani da Bahaushe kan yi ta hanyar hikima cikin ‘yan kalmomi kaɗan”

3. Ma'anar Ruwa

3.1 Ma'anar Ruwa ta Mahangar Addini

Ruwa na daga cikin manyan ni'imomin da Allah (Madaukakin Sarki) Ya yi wa halittunsa, kuma shi ne tushen rayuwa ga dukkan halittu da suke rayuwa a doron kasa. Muhimmancin ruwa ya bayyana a cikin Alkur'ani Mai Girma inda Allah Ya ce: "*Kuma Mun sanya daga ruwa kowane abu mai rai*" (Al-Anbiya'i, 21:30). Wannan aya ta nuna cewa ruwa shi ne ginshikin samuwar rayuwa da ci gabanta. Haka kuma, Allah Ya saukar da ruwa daga sama domin amfanin mutane, dabbobi da tsirrai, wanda hakan yake tabbatar da muhimmancin ruwa ga dorewar rayuwa da wadatar muhalli (An-Nahl, 16:10–11).

3.2 Ma'anar Ruwa ta Mahangar Kimiyya

Masana kimiyya sun tabbatar da abin da nassosin Alkur'ani suka yi nuni da shi dangane da muhimmancin ruwa ga rayuwa. A cewar *United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization* (2024), ruwa muhimmiyar hanya ce da take tallafawa rayuwa, samar da abinci, lafiya, makamashi da ci gaban tattalin arziki a duniya. Bugu da kari, rahotannin *United States Geological Survey* sun nuna cewa kusan kashi 71% na saman doron kasa ruwa ne ya mamaye shi, yayin da mafi yawan wannan ruwa yake cikin tekuna da sauran manyan ma'ajiyoyin ruwa na duniya (USGS, 2024). Wannan ya hada da tekuna, gulabe, tafkuna, koguna, koramu da kuma ruwan da suke karkashin kasa, wadanda dukkansu suke taka muhimmiyar rawa wajen raya muhalli da halittu.

Saboda haka, ruwa ba kawai wata ni'ima ba ce ta Allah (Madaukakin Sarki), har ila yau wata muhimmiyar kadara ce ta rayuwa da ci gaba. Wannan ne ya sa masana addini, muhalli da kimiyya suke jaddada muhimmancin kiyaye albarkatun ruwa da amfani da su cikin hikima domin tabbatar da dorewar rayuwar al'umma da sauran halittun duniya.

A Kamusun Hausa (2006), an ba da ma'anar ruwa kamar haka: Ruwa (ruwaa sn, nj, jm, ruwayee ko ruwaiwai); abu garai-garai maras launi ko fanshi, kuma ana wanka da wanki da dafa abinci da wanke-wanke da makamantansu da shi-----ruwan sama, ruwan rijjiya, ruwan teku, ruwan famfo da dai sauransu.

A cewar *Biology Online Dictionary* (2023), ruwa wani sinadari ne mai muhimmanci ga rayuwa wanda yake samuwa a yanayi uku: ruwa (*liquid*), tururi (*gas*), da kankara (*solid*). A cewar Shiklomanov (1993) ya nuna cewa ruwa albarkatun halitta ne mai muhimmanci, amma ruwan dandano da ake iya amfani da shi yana da iyaka idan aka kwatanta da yawan ruwan da ke doron kasa.

Haka kuma, Mays (2011), ruwa muhimmin albarkatun kasa ne wanda rayuwar dan Adam da ci gaban tattalin arziki suka dogara a kansa.

A cewar *Encyclopaedia Britannica* (2026), ruwa wani sinadari ne da ya kunshi *hydrogen* da *oxygen* (H₂O), wanda yake samuwa a yanayi uku: ruwa (*liquid*), tururi (*gas*), da kankara (*solid*), kuma yana da matuƙar muhimmanci ga rayuwar halittu.

3.3 Ma'anar Ruwa a Fannin Noma

A cewar FAO (2020) Ruwa wani muhimmin albarkatun halitta ne a fannin noma, wanda ake amfani da shi wajen ban ruwa, samar da amfanin gona, kiwon dabbobi, da kiyaye lafiyar kasa. Rashin wadataccen ruwa na iya rage yawan amfanin gona da ingancin aikin noma.

Haka kuma, *United States Department of Agriculture* (2022) ta bayyana ruwa a matsayin muhimmin albarkatu da ake amfani da shi wajen ban ruwa, samar da amfanin gona, da tabbatar da dorewar aikin noma.

3.4 Ma'anar Ruwa a Fannin Kiwon Lafiya

A fannin kiwon lafiya, ruwa ana kallon a matsayin wani muhimmin sinadari da jiki yake bukata domin rayuwa, kula da lafiya, da hana yaduwar cututtuka.

WHO (2026) ta bayyana cewa ruwa mai tsafra da tsafar muhalli (WASH) suna da matuƙar muhimmanci ga lafiyar ɗan Adam da walwalarsa, kuma samun isasshen ruwa mai tsafra yana taimakawa wajen hana cututtuka da inganta lafiya. Haka kuma ta kara bayyana cewa ruwa mai tsafra da sauƙin samu yana da muhimmanci ga lafiyar jama'a, domin ana amfani da shi wajen sha, girki, tsafra, da sauran buƙatun yau da kullum da ke kare lafiyar ɗan Adam.

3.5 Amfanin Ruwa

Amfanin ruwa ya fi gaban a kididdige ko a yi bayanin sa a cikin ‘yan jumloji, sai dai a yi ɗan koƙarin da za a iya yi a bar saura, domin rayuwa ba ta yi sai da ruwa. Noma sai da ruwa, in an noma kayan gona an kawo gida, duk abin da za a sarrafa daga cikin kayan gonar nan tilas sai an haɗa da ruwa yake inganta kafin ya zamo abin da ake son ya zama. Ana haɗa abubuwa da dama don a samu biyan wasu buƙatu ta hanyar haɗa su da ruwa. Babban misali a nan shi ne; abinci abu mai muhimmancin gaske wajen dora rayuwa, to kuma babu yadda za a yi a kammala shi ba tare da sanya ruwa ba. Bugu da ƙari, ana haɗa magunguna da ruwa misali; ganye iri daban-daban, da saƙe-saƙi da sauransu, duk ana haɗa su wuri ɗaya tare da ruwa don magani har a kira su da suna ruwan maganin kaza, kamar ruwan sassken madacci, da ruwan sassaken dalbejiya, sannan da uwa-uba ruwan zamzam.

4. Ra'in Mazhabar Gudummuwar Adabi ga Al'umma

Wannan mazhaba ta gudummuwar adabi ga al'umma ta fi mayar da hankali ne ga rawar da adabi yake takawa a hali na zamantakewa. Haka kuma tana duba yadda adabi yake tafiya da al'adu da fasahohi na al'umma da yadda suke daɗa inganta rukunonin rayuwa.

“Ana iya amfani da wannan mazhaba a adabin baka da yadda yake shafar ayyuka na sana'oi da sauran ayyuka madanganta al'adun jama'a”. Gusau, (2015)

5. Gurbin Ruwa a Karin Maganar Hausa

Ruwa ya taka muhimmiyar rawa a cikin karin maganar Hausa. Haka kuma, ruwa ba ƙaramin tasiri yake da shi ba ga kowace rayuwa da take bisa doron ƙasa da ƙarƙashinta da kuma cikin sammai. Saboda sanin amfanin ruwa wanda ya ke ba a rayuwa sai da su, ya sa Bahaushen ya kula da su wajen ba su matsayin da ya dace da su a cikin ma'amalolinsa na yau da kullum. A kan haka, duk wani motsi da yawan tu'ammali da Bahaushen yakan yi da ruwa yakan samu karin maganar da ta dace ya kulla ko ya ƙirƙira cikin fasaha domin ya zo daidai da saƙon da yake nufin isarwa ga al'umma ta hanyar amfani da “ruwa”. Bunza, (2006 shf 12) ya ce; “Ruwa dangin rai ne, babu rayuwar da ke yi ba da ruwa ba”

5.1 Gurbin Ruwa Cikin Karin Magana mai Alaƙa da Mutane

Daga cikin ire-iren karin maganar da Bahaushen ya ƙirƙira don ya samu biyan buƙatarsa wajen sadarwa akwai waɗanda suka shafi mutane kai tsaye, domin da an ambace su kuma aka saurare su saurare na basira za a fahinci cewa suna da alaƙa da ayyukan da mutane suke aiwatarwa na yau da kullum. Ma'ana, mutane suna da kaso mai yawa a cikin bayanin karin maganar da ta shafi ruwa. Daga cikin misalan karin magana masu nuni da ayyukan mutane da wannan takarda ta kawo akwai:

Aikin banza ɗibar ruwa da homa

Ai ƙara wa gari ruwa ba wata matsala ba ce

Ba a ce wa ma ci wake ya sha ruwa
Ba a taka ruwa a dibi ruwa
Ba baƙo ruwa ka sha labari
Ba ta sabuwa bindiga a ruwa
Kowa ya sayi rariya ya san tana zubar da ruwa
Kowaz zubar da ruwa don ya ji sanyi ne.
Rijiya da babu guga, shan ruwanta sai da alƙawali
Ruwan da ya buge ka shi ne ruwa
Ruwa ga wuya maganin maki wanka
Ruwan roko ba su dafa wake
Ruwan roko ba su wankan zawo
Ruwan ƙorama mai sha da ɗan gida da baƙo
Rijiya ta ba da ruwa guga ta hana

5.2 Gurbin Ruwa a Cikin Karin Magana mai Alaka da Dabbobi da Kwari

Su kuma waɗannan nau'ukan karin magana suna bayani ne a kan irin yadda sunayen dabbobi da ƙwari suka fito/bayyana a cikinsu. Ana da masaniyar cewa, dabbobi da ƙwari suna da muhimmancin ga rayuwar mutum kamar yadda mutum kamar yadda mutum yake da muhimmanci ga tasu rayuwar, musamman dabbobin gida waɗanda mutum ke yankawa ya ci irin shanu, tumaki, ko ya yi kiyoyi don alfarma irin su dawaki da sauransu. Waɗannan karin maganganu da ke ƙasa suna da dangantaka da dabbobi da ƙwari waɗanda Bahausha yake mu'amala da su, a gida ko a daji Misali:

Albarkacin kaza ƙadangare kan sha ruwan kasko
A kai godiya ruwa ina akalar jan ta?
An wanke gargaza da ruwanta
Cinikin kifi ruwa
Inda akuyar gaba ta sha ruwa, nan ta baya ke sha
In da ruwa gara ta yi gini, in babu ruwa gara ta yi gini
In ka ji zuma shina ƙugi to ya yi ruwa
In da amana ruwa ba ya dafa kifi ba
Kura na shan ruwa kare na kallo/leƙo/rego

Kwado ya kirayi ruwa sun ci shi

Ruwa duk na kwado ne amma ban da na zafi

Ruwa ya ce ba ni na dafa kifi ba wuta ce

Ruwa ya fare wa dan kada bai gama wanka ba

Mai hankali ka ba kaza ruwa da damana

Tsuntsun da ya kira ruwa, shi ruwa kan doka

5.3 Gurbi Ruwa a Cikin Karin Magana mai Alaka da Tsirrai

Daga cikin halittun da ke amfani da ruwa akwai tsirrai. Tsirrai su ne kananan shuke-shuke da ke fitowa a cikin gonakin saman tudu ko a cikin fadama, domin amfanin dan'Adam. Misali irin su albasa, barkono, sure/yakuwa, da yalo da sauransu. Dukkan wadannan ba su rayuwa sai da taimakon ruwa. Ganin haka, sai Bahaushe ya yi tattalin gina karin magana da ire-iren wadannan shuke-shuke kamar haka;

Albasa ba ta yi halin ruwa ba

Idan albasa ta samu taki da gyara kuma har ta girma ta kosa aka cire ta, to yaji take yi sosai in an yanka ta, amma su ruwa da suka zama su ne mahaifarta sanyi gare su ke nan ana kallon ta gadi hali irin na uwarta, sai ba ta yi hakanan ba ta buge da yaji ana yanka ana zubar da hawaye. Ga zahirin rayuwar yau da kullum idan misali, mutune suka haifi da sai aka ga ba ya irin halinsu sai a ce "albasa ba ta yi halin ruwa ba".

Ban ruwan albasa, a diba kasa a zuba kasa

In an ba albasa ruwa a zan ba yalo

5.4 Gurbir Ruwa a Cikin Karin Magana mai Alaka da Yanayi

Yanayi shi ne halin da muka tsinci kanmu a cikin muhallinmu ko kuma irin halin da wasu abubuwa suke ciki ko sukan kasancewa a halin rayuwa ta yau da kullum. Bahaushe bai yi kasa a guiwa wajen yi ma yanayin da muke ciki kallon kwaƙwaf ba, aka gina karin magana a kansu. Daga cikin wadannan karin maganganu akwai:

An kai ruwa rana

A shekara saran ruwa sai tumbatsi

Ba kyau ba ga dakin gona, shi dai ya yi maganin ruwa

Daidai kurji, daidai ruwansa

Daidai ruwa, daidai gari

Dukan ruwa ba ya hana gwarje amonsa

In ta yi ruwa rijiya, in ba ta yi ba masai

In ruwa ya zube ya bar tulu da dama

Jini ya fi ruwa guibi
Kumfar mai ba dai da na ruwa ba
Ƙwaryar da aka gina rijiya da ita, ba a shan ruwa da ita
Ƙarshen ruwa kware
Kyawon ruwa su koma inda suka fito
Mayar da ruwa rijiya ba barna ba
Ruwa ba ya tsami banza, in babu farau-farau da surki
Ruwa ba sa tsami banza, in ba gari da nono
Ruwa ba su cin sakaina
Ruwa ba sa'ar kwando ba ne
Ruwan dadi maganin ƙishin ruwa
Sanyin mai (man shanu danye) ba dai da na ruwa ba
Sakaina sarkin iya ruwa

5.5 Gurbin Ruwa a Cikin Karin Magana Mai Alaka da Muhalli

Muhalli shi ne wurin da mutane suke zaune da kewayensa, wato kamar ƙasar da muke rayuwa a samanta. Kamar yadda za a gani a nan, wasu karin maganganu ne Bahaushe ya kirkiro ta amfani da sunan ruwa, waɗanda suka danganci yanayin muhallinmu. Misali;

“An dade ana sheka ruwa ƙasa tana shanyewa”

Idan aka ce ‘sheka ruwa’ ana nufin ruwan sama da Allah Maɗaukakin Sarki yake saukarwa daga sama zuwa doron ƙasa, kuma babbar ni’imar da yake ba halittu a lokuta daban-daban da yankuna daban-daban na duniya. Ƙasa kuma, ita ce ke shimfiɗe wadda halittu suke zaune a kanta. Wannan karin magana tana nufin; aikata wani al’amari da ake yi ko yausha kuma yana wucewa. Ga misali:

“Ruwa ran ƙasa, ciyawa suma”

Kamar a can sama cikin wancan karin magana da aka yi bayanin cewa, ƙasa tana shanye ruwan sama da ake saukowa daga sararin sama, ba don komi ba sai don saboda wannan irin karin magana da ya ke cewa; ‘ruwa su ne ran ƙasa’ da sauran halittu da ke rayuwa a ban ƙasa. Idan an yi ruwan sama ƙasa ta tsotsa har ta adana wasu ƙarƙashinta don amfanin wasu abubuwa a wata rana. Idan babu ruwa a saman ƙasa, akwai matsala don za ta bushe ya kasance ba a sami cikakken amfanin gona da ya kamata a samu ba.

6. Bayanin Manufar Wasu Karin Maganganu da Kalmar Ruwa ta Fito a Cikinsu.

A wannan gabar an yi bayani tare da fito da manufar wasu karin maganganu da suka fito da kalmar ruwa a cikinsu kamar haka:

“Aikin banza dībar ruwa da homa”

Dibar ruwa ta kowace hanya an san cewa mutum yana aiwatar da shi tare da amfani da kayan aiki iri-iri, misali guga/wasaki da kwarya ko roba ko bokiti da sauransu. An sani cewa ‘homa’ ba ta cikin kayan aikin dībar ruwa, saboda irin yanayinta ba na wannan aiki ba ne. An yi homa ne don aikin kamun kifi, idan kuma mutum ya kuskura ya yi amfani da homa domin dībar ruwa zai yi aikin banza ne. Ga rayuwa ta zahiri idan mutum yana aikata wani aiki da ba ya da amfani sai a ce masa yana “aikin banza dībar ruwa da homa”.

“Ai kara wa gari ruwa ba barna ba ce”

Gari (garii) wani nau’in abinci ne da ake samarwa daga tsabar gero, ko dawa ko makamantansu. Ana iya yin gumba da gari a sha, ko a yi farau-farau a sha. To shi ne Bahaushe ya kirkiiri karin magana da nufin bayyana cewa; ba a yi barna ba don an kara wa ruwan farau-farau wasu ruwa don bai hana a yi amfani da shi.

“Ba a ce wa ma ci wake ya sha ruwa”

Daga cikin nau’ukan abincin da ake ci a sha ruwa da yawa, wake yana ciki. To a nan, Bahaushe ya saka wannan cikin karin magana domin yi wa al’umma kashedi ga aikata wani al’amari don kada a wuce gona da iri, kuma shi mutum ana nuna masa kada ya aikata wata barna, idan har ya aikata to ba sai an gaya mishi ya dawo ya gyara ba.

“Inda saniyar gaba ta sha ruwa, nan ta baya ke sha”

An san dabbobi irin shanu suna tafiya wajen kiwo tare duk inda za su je, to a cikinsu akwai shugaba wadda ita ke yin jagorancin tafiyar. Ma’ana, a cikin yawace-yawacen da suke yi na kiwo duk wuɓɓu da ta tsaya ta ci wani abinci da ta gani a gabanta, nan na bayanta suke tsayawa. Haka har wajen shan ruwansu wurin ta gaba ta sha, to ta baya ma nan za ta tsaya ta sha. Wannan ne Bahaushe ya yi kokarin bayyanawa a cikin wannan karin magana. A zahirin rayuwa kuwa, kamar mutum ne da magoya bayansa kusan duk abin da ya aikata sai na bayansa sun yi saboda ana ganin dābi’arsu ta zama tare.

“In da ruwa gara ta yi gini, in babu ruwa ta yi gini”

Gara (garaa) wata halitta ce daga cikin kwarin da suke rayuwa a cikin kasa. Babban aikin wadannan kwari mai ban mamaki shi ne ginari da suke yi. Misalin wannan a rayuwar mutane kuma shi ne; kamar mutum ne mai hali/wadata ko ta halin kaka yana iya yin ayyukansa. Haka ita ma gara muna gani tana gininta ko babu ruwa.

“An kai ruwa rana”

In an ce ‘an kai ruwa rana’ to an shiga wani yanayi ko wani hali mara dadi. An kwatanta wannan karin magana ne da irin yadda mutane suke yi idan an yi rasuwa lokacin sanyi a da, sai a kai ruwa cikin rana a aje don su rage sanyi a yi amfani da su wajen yi wa gawa wanka. Idan wani al’amari ya baci ko wata rigima ta ki ci ta ki cinyewa sai, a ce an kai ruwa rana ko kuma idan jayayya ta shiga tsakanin wasu har aka kai wajen shiga tsakaninsu.

“Ruwa ba ya tsami banza, in ba gari da nono”

Kowane abu yana da yanayin da aka halicce shi da shi, haka shi ma ruwa an halicce shi maras launi, kuma ba su da wani dandano ma'ana narai-narai suke. In wani abu ya haɗu da ruwan da ke lafiya lau, to dole yanayinsu na halitta da aka san su da shi ya sauya. Ko dai launin dandano, ko wari, ko tsami da sauransu. A bayanin wannan karin magana in an dube ta ana nufin wani abu bai faruwa haka kawai, wato sai da wani dalili kamar yadda ruwa ba su tsami banza sai dai in wani abu ya shiga cikinsu.

“Ƙarshen ruwa kware”

Komi na duniya yana da muhallinsa inda aka san shi. Ruwa suna yawatawa cikin duniya wato, ba su tsayawa wuri ɗaya, face na tafukka/tafkuna da sauransu. An yi amfani da wannan karin magana ne don a nuna cewa; komi da inda ake ajiye shi kamar yadda ruwa suke gangarawa su isa mazauninsu wato, gulabe da koramu da sauransu. A zahirin rayuwa kuma, misali idan aka haɗa mutum da Allah, don ya yi wani abu ko don ya bar wani abu ya ƙi, ana kuma sane da cewa duk wanda bai yi wa Allah ba zai yi wa banza. Duk lokacin da ya yi wa banza ana iya yi masa gori/haɓaici da wannan karin magana.

7. Kammalawa

Wannan takarda ta fito da karin maganganun da suka ƙunshi kalmar ruwa, kasancewar ruwa abu ne mai muhimmancin gaske. Haka kuma ana yawan amfani da ita tsakanin mutane, ba tare da la'akari da irin rawar da take takawa a cikin wani ɓangare na karin magana ba. Kalmar ruwa ta yi tasiri ƙwarai da gaske a cikin karin maganar Hausa, inda za a fahimci haka kuma shi ne, duk ɗaukacin karin maganar da aka kawo a cikin wannan takarda suna ƙunshe da kalmar ruwa. Bayan wannan kuma Hausawa sun yi amfani da basira da hikima da fasahar da Allah ya ba su wajen ƙirƙiro karin magana da suka shafi mutane da sunayen wasu dabbobi da ƙwari da wasu itatuwa da tsirrai da muhalli da yanayi, suka gina karin magana da su, da zimmakar fitowa da al'adunsu.

Manazarta

Biology Online. (2023). *Water*. Biology Online Dictionary.

<https://www.biologyonline.com/dictionary/water>

Bunza A. M (2002). *“Rubutun Hausa (Yadda Yake da Yadda Ake Yin Sa) Don Masu koyo Da Koyarwa”* Wallafar Ibrash Islamic Publications Center L.T.D 31, Adelabu Street, Surulere , Lagos.

Bunza, A. M. (2006). *Gadon Fede Al'ada. Tiwal Nigeria Limited Surulere Lagos.*

Bunza, A. M. (2015) *“Arashi Shi gogi BaƘauye”*. (Nazarin Karin Maganar Arashi Da ke Jikin Motoci). Takardar da aka gabatar a taron ƙara wa juna sani, sashen koyar da Harsunan Najeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.

Bunza, A. M. (2015). Gaskiya A Tunanin Bahaushen Karin Magana. Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sokoto.

Dangambo, A. (1984). *“Rabe-Raben Adabin Hausa da Muhimmancisa Ga Rayuwar Hausawa”* Madaba'ar Kamfanin 'Triumph' Gidan Sa'adu Zungur, Kano Services Limited, Kaduna.

Danhausu A. M (2012). *Hausa mai Dubun Hikima*. Century Research and publishing company, Abuja Kano Kaduna Lagos Zaria.

Dantumbishi A. M (2012). *“Harshe, Al'umma da kuma Zamananci”* Muƙalar da aka samu a Cikin Mujallar Dundaye, Jami'ar Usmanu Dan Fodiyo Sokoto.

Danyaya , B. M. (2007) Karin Maganar Hausawa Makarantar Hausa, No. 1 Ubandoma Road (Sabon Titi) Sokoto.

Encyclopaedia Britannica. (2026). *Water*. In *Britannica*.

<https://www.britannica.com/science/water>

- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2020). *The State of Food and Agriculture 2020: Overcoming water challenges in agriculture*. Rome: FAO
- Gummi, A. M. (Trans.). (2013). *Alkur'ani mai girma da tarjamar ma'anoninsa zuwa ga harshen Hausa*. King Fahd Glorious Qur'an Printing Complex.
- Gusau, S. M (2015) *Mazhabobin Ra'i Da Tarke A Adabi Da Al'adu Na Hausa*. Century Research and Publishing Limited Kano-Nigeria
- Junaidu, I. da Yar'aduwa, T. M. (2007). "*Harshe Da Adabin Hausa A Kammale , Don Manyan Makarantun Sakandare*". Spectrum Books Limited, Ibadan.
- Koko, H. S. (2011). *Hausa cikin Hausa*. Mathi Production, Sokoto.
- Koko, H. S.(1989). *Karin Magana A Hannun Mata A Garin Sakkwato*" Kundin digiri na farko, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Malumfashi I.A da Ibrahim N. (2014). *Kamusun Karin Maganar Hausa*. Bugun Makarantar Malam Bambadiya Gida mai lamba 15 Lawal Abubakar Road Unguwar Dosa, Kaduna-Nijeriya.
- Mays, L. W. (2011). *Water resources engineering* (2nd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Muhammad Y. M. (2005). "*Adabin Hausa*" Dab'in Ahmadu Bello University press Ltd. P.M.B 1094, Samaru-zaria Nijeriya
- Nahuce, M. I. (2008). "*Karin Maganar Hausa A Rubuce*" Kundin Digiri na Biyu, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Rigacikun M. A. (2013). "*Hikimomin Rayuwa A. Sigar: Labaru da Waƙoƙi da Kacici-kacici da Karin Magana*" Limawa Serene ventures, No. D 1 Liman Abubakar Iyal Street, Rigacikun, Kaduna.
- Sanyinna, Y. L da Sifawa, T. M. (2015) *Tsaro a Cikin Karin Magana*. Mujallar Shagari Journal of Languages, Bugun Farko, Kwalejin Ilimi ta Shehu Shagari Sakkwato.
- Shiklomanov, I. A. (1993). World fresh water resources. In P. H. Gleick (Ed.), Water in Crisis: A Guide to the World's Fresh Water Resources (pp. 13–24). Oxford University Press.*
- Tudun Wada, Y. Y. (1989). "*Hausa A Dunkule; (Sabon Tsari)*". Madaba'ar Kamfanin 'Triumph' Gidan Sa'adu Zungur, Kano.
- Umar M. B, (1980) "*Adabin Baka*". Hausa Publications Centre, Mangwaron Babajo, Zaria City, P.O Box 675 Zaria.
- United States Department of Agriculture. (2022). Agriculture and Water Resources. Washington, DC: USDA.*
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2024). *Water security and sustainable development*. <https://www.unesco.org/en/water-security-and-sustainable-development>
- United States Geological Survey. (2024). *How much water is there on Earth?* <https://www.usgs.gov/special-topics/water-science-school/science/how-much-water-there-earth>
- World Health Organization. (2026). *Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH)*. Geneva: WHO.
- Yahya I. Y. da Dangambo. A. (1986). "*Jagoran Nazarin Hausa*". N.N.P.C Limited P.O Box 412 Zaria.